

Electronic Mentoring: How Can It Be Used with Teachers?

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Abstract : Electronic mentoring is defined as a relationship between a mentor and a mentee using computer mediated communication (CMC) that is intended to develop and improve mentee's skills, confidence, and cultural understanding. This session will increase knowledge about electronic mentoring, its uses, and outcomes. The research behind electronic mentoring and descriptions of existing programs will also be shared.

Keywords : electronic mentoring, mentoring, beginning special educators, education

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